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GATHERING AND SHARING NEW METHODS AND TECHNIQUES TO APPLY 21ST CENTURY PEDAGOGY IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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Interactivity, motivation, gamification, teamwork, real problem solving are keywords to the 21st century pedagogy [1] and they were also the topics of the workshop. Regarding these topics many questions arise: How can new dimensions of teaching and learning be applied in the engineering education? How can the efficiency of contact hours at the university be increased to develop 21st century skills? Which new methods can be used on a lecture with more than a hundred students?

Theory and numerous new techniques are presented in literature [2] which are easy to use and ready to use in most of the subjects, however it still seems difficult to teach the mathematical and mechanical bases which require deep understanding and lots of practice. The traditional informational role of the teachers is changed [3, 4], hence lecturers and teachers face new challenges also in high education. They must not only motivate their students but also handle numerous consultations simultaneously, in order to fulfil their supporting and helping role.

The aim of this workshop was to gather and share innovative, new methodological techniques and ideas of the participants which have already been efficiently applied in engineering education all around the world. Recently, several interactive techniques and ICT based methods were built in the authors' subjects. The pilot programs proved to be successful both in moderate size practicals (about 30 students) and in large size lectures (more than 100 students).

The applied methods were presented through a real-life experience. The knowledge and feedbacks of the participants were collected by the innovative techniques used in the above subjects. During the workshop the participants were invited for a gamified interactive teamwork, in which different (mostly ICT) methods served to gather information. Within the program the participants could:

- watch a short video (**motivation**)

- fill an interactive attendance sheet (to demonstrate **attitude change** [5])
- have a look inside an online escape room (test preparation practice in Base of Structural Design subject), and try to escape (**gamification** [6]),
- draw online diagrams together (**teamwork, collaborative learning**),
- vote online (methodological point of views: continuous **interaction**, feedback, effect on the teaching process),
- solve individual numerical problems (**flipped classroom** theory or hybrid methods [7], problem solving, differentiation),
- collect evaluation alternatives (motivation, gamification, **psychology of gift giving**).

During these activities a lot of information was collected about not only the presented but also all the other 21st century engineering educational techniques. As a result, a collection was draw up about which are the main trends in engineering education, at the time being, what are the pedagogical aims of the participants, and which innovative direction they are moving on. Participants could share their actually used and suggested teaching methods and technologies (devices, applications) on online surfaces. Ideas were gathered regarding to the evaluation and motivation techniques as well. With the help of the gathered information our questions were answered as it is given below.

18 persons participated in the workshop.

Task 1.

By filling an interactive attendance sheet participants wrote their personal pedagogical aims, what they expect from this conference. According to the handwritten answers, participants aimed to get inspired by new teaching methods, to use new technological tools and to establish network with other colleagues.

Task 2.

Estimation the effectiveness of the traditional and the present teaching methods in percentage by the participants. Results: Participants estimated in average 44,5% the effectiveness of their own contact lessons.

Task 3.

Tendencies and directions of innovation in the 21st century according to the participants. Results: Most of the participants have already started to apply some new learner-centered teaching techniques. The next table contains the number of the participants voted for the different new tendencies as the most efficient way of modern teaching.

Tendencies in High Education			
Hibrid teaching	Collaborative learning	Growing Focus on Measuring Learning	Redesigning Learning Spaces
6	8	1	3

Task 4.

Collecting the actually used and suggested teaching methods, devices, technology, applications etc. from the participants in groupwork. Results can be found in the link below: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1bfMEbfu0fgr1O-k0jLazibeM-K55EGEpWs1SQosq4CE/edit#gid=0>

The table contains 16 different teaching technologies and methods gathered from the participants with the applied applications and tools, completed with a short description of the method, with important connected links and with notes why the participants suggest using them.

Task 5.

Evaluation of the workshop. Results: Participants estimated in average 60% the effectiveness of the common work and the present workshop.

